

Speakers for Inspirational Talks

We are looking for a few speakers from the attached list to give inspirational talks. Please take a look at the suggestions listed at the link below and enter the names from the spreadsheet of your top five picks. You may continue entering your rankings up to ten people, but only the first five are required. The spreadsheet gives you the names of the suggested people and some helpful information to make your choices. Please submit your input by Thursday at 2pm ET.

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1CP6uteMOxZhqr80tmL00TBNDh7M4Ycc6IKjZIN0hK3w/edit?usp=sharing>

* Indicates required question

1. Email *

2. Top rated choice *

3. Second rated choice *

4. Third rated choice *

5. Fourth rated choice *

6. Fifth rated choice *

7. Sixth rated choice

8. Seventh rated choice

9. Eighth rated choice

10. Ninth rated choice

11. Tenth rated choice

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